

Comparison and Evaluation of Speech to Text in Italian for Understanding Dementia

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Abstract. Dementia is a neurodegenerative disease characterized by decreased cognitive functions, including memory and problem-solving. Monitoring the progression of dementia is essential to improve quality of life, adapt treatment, avoid potential complications, and help family members to understand what to expect and how to behave. Conventional diagnostic methods are based on questionnaires distributed by doctors and require time-consuming procedures, as the person must travel to the facility. Models based on deep learning techniques, such as large language models (LLMs), are emerging as promising resources to improve the speech-to-text and text-to-speech techniques that can support the diagnosis. These models require considerable computational power, especially for real-time operations.

This work presents a comparative study to identify the best combination of speech-to-text systems and spelling correction for real-time applications on device with a non-essential hardware. We evaluate three speech-to-text systems: Whisher Tiny, Whisher Base, and Vosk, along with two spelling correction methods. The systems were trained and tested using a publicly available Italian dataset, called Common Voice dataset. The results show that Whisher Base outperforms both Whisher Tiny and Vosk. Furthermore, the performance of Whisher, with and without spelling correction, is comparable when background noise levels are low.

Keywords: Speech-to-text Systems Evaluation · spelling correction · Dementia.

1 Introduction

Dementia is a syndrome characterized by a progressive decline in cognitive function across various domains, consequently impairing functional abilities, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) [5]. Currently, over 55 million people worldwide are affected by dementia, with more than 60% residing in low- and middle-income countries, and each year, nearly 10 million new cases

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are diagnosed [7]. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5 (DSM-5) lists 13 possible causes of dementia [14]. However, Alzheimer’s disease (AD) is the cause in about 70% of all cases [24], while other causes include Lewy body disease, brain injuries, blood vessel problems, and frontotemporal dementia [6]. Early detection and continuous monitoring of disease progress are crucial, as it enables timely interventions to management of the disease and improve the quality of life for affected individuals, through both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment strategies [17]. Moreover, understanding the course of the syndrome helps caregivers and their families cope with changing needs and prepare for future challenges. Questionnaires are widely used in dementia screening and monitoring. The Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) is the most widely used tool for diagnosing dementia and is considered the gold standard for cognitive screening. Other screening tools, such as the AD8 [15] and Mini-Cog and Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) [11], are also used.

Although these methods provide valuable insights, they are time-consuming and often require patients to visit healthcare facilities, which may be inconvenient or burdensome for individuals with mobility issues or those in the later stages of the disease. Automated tools that can monitor the progression of dementia syndrome with the possibility of administering non-pharmacological treatments, such as cognitive training personalized according to one’s level of education and personality, are of fundamental importance. Recent advances in artificial intelligence have introduced new possibilities for supporting the monitoring of dementia syndrome and cognitive training. Different results have been reached in that area. Recent advances in artificial intelligence have introduced new possibilities for supporting the monitoring of dementia syndrome and cognitive training. For example, smartphone apps like Sea Hero Quest assess spatial navigation skills, which are often impaired in early dementia [12]. At the same time, AI models that take wearable device data as input allow us to track physical activity and sleep patterns, potential early indicators of dementia [27]. On the other hand, the new improvement of speech-to-text and text-to-speech technologies via large language models (LLMs) have shown promise in automating and improving diagnostic processes. These models can process and analyze speech in real time, offering potential benefits in clinical settings where rapid assessments are needed. However, the computational power required to run these models, especially in real-time applications, remains challenging, mainly when using devices with limited hardware capabilities.

This paper presents a comparative study aimed at identifying the optimal combination of speech-to-text systems and spelling correction methods for real-time applications on devices with constrained computational resources. We evaluate three widely used speech-to-text systems, i.e., Whisper-tiny, Whisper-Base [23], and Vosk API [1], along with two different spelling correction approaches. To ensure the generalizability of our findings, we train and test the systems using a publicly available Italian dataset, called Common Voice dataset. Our results demonstrate that Whisper-Base outperforms both Whisper-tiny and Vosk in terms of accuracy and efficiency. Additionally, we show that the performance of

Whisper, with and without spelling correction, is comparable when background noise levels are low. Finally, we integrate Whisper into a demo application to evaluate their effectiveness in real-world scenarios, providing a proof of concept for their potential use in dementia monitoring.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section ??, we introduce the basic knowledge related to deep learning models. Section 2 describes the main automatic speech recognition systems, from early-stage approaches to modern methods based on deep learning architectures. Section 3 introduces the performed experiments and the selected toolkit’s main reasons. The paper ends with some conclusions and future works, Section 4.

2 Overview of Automatic Speech Recognition

ASR, or automatic speech recognition, is the technology that recognizes and converts spoken language into text. It is applied in various scenarios, such as voice assistants, media applications, and voice-command systems. ASR has witnessed remarkable progress, revolutionizing human-computer interaction across diverse domains [18, 19]. Nevertheless, this progress has not been uniformly distributed across all languages. Figure 1 shows some recent improvements in speech recognition models from the Google Voice Search app, introduced in 2010, to Whispers, presented in 2023.

Fig. 1. A timeline of some of the significant advances in speech recognition from 2010 to 2023

In the early stages, manual feature extraction and standard approaches such as Gaussian Mixture Models and Hidden Markov Model have been developed and used. These architectures were most suitable for addressing fundamental issues,

as their limitations might complicate large-scale, complex real-world problems. Recently, models such as RNNs and CNNs, as well as Transformers, were applied to ASR with considerable success. ASR models like Wav2Vec, Wav2Vec2, HuBERT, Whisper, and WavLM have significantly improved the accuracy and robustness of ASR systems, paving the way for more efficient and reliable STT transcription technologies.

Wav2Vec Wav2Vec is an end-to-end architecture that utilizes self-supervised learning, combining transformer and convolutional layers [25]. The model employs a multi-layer convolutional feature encoder to transform raw audio waveforms into latent speech representations. These latent representations are input to the network, which is transformer-masked. The self-supervised learning objective is defined by the discrete outputs generated when the transformer network quantizes the continuous representations. These quantized representations are contextualized by the transformer module’s attention blocks, producing a set of discrete contextual representations. The feature encoder consists of seven convolutional blocks with 512 channels. The transformer network consists of 24 blocks, each having 1024 dimensions, 4096 inner dimensions, and a total of 16 attention heads.

DiscreteBERT DiscreteBERT is an adaptation of the BERT architecture designed to process discrete token inputs instead of continuous token embeddings [21]. This modification makes it particularly suitable for handling tokenized inputs from various sources, such as audio or text, where the tokens represent distinct information units. Unlike traditional models that operate in a unidirectional manner (either left-to-right or right-to-left), DiscreteBERT can understand the context in both directions. It uses a transformer architecture that employs self-attention mechanisms to assess the importance of each token within the sequence. Additionally, DiscreteBERT is trained using Masked Language Modeling (MLM), where the model learns to predict randomly masked tokens in the input sequence, improving its ability to capture and understand the broader context of the language.

Whisper. Whisper is a model developed by OpenAI based on integrating supervised and self-supervised learning techniques [23]. It is trained on a diverse dataset of 680,000 hours of multilingual and multitask supervised data, allowing it to learn robust representations from noisy audio. This approach performs well in transcribing speech accurately across a variety of languages and tasks, making it ideal for real-world applications. Whisper excels in challenging scenarios, improving speech recognition even in difficult conditions. Additionally, it is capable of performing multiple speech-related tasks effectively.

WavLM WavLM is an ASR model developed by researchers that integrates concepts from ASR and language modelling [13]. The model extends the self-supervised learning framework to language modelling for speech, with the goal of improving the contextual understanding of spoken language. By pre-training on

large-scale, unlabeled speech corpora, WavLM learns contextual representations that capture the underlying semantics of spoken language. This approach eliminates the need for text transcriptions during pre-training, making the model highly scalable and applicable to a wide range of languages and dialects. Its performance remains competitive across various ASR tasks, demonstrating its effectiveness in capturing the complexities of spoken language in real-world scenarios. Notably, WavLM extends self-supervised learning to language modelling by directly extracting contextual information from raw audio signals. At the same time, its scalability allows it to handle large-scale datasets, further contributing to its strong performance.

Kaldi and Vosk Kaldi and Vosk are powerful speech recognition toolkits with distinctive features and capabilities that address various user needs. Kaldi is known for its flexibility, which allows for extensive customization of speech recognition systems and supports some models. Its comprehensive toolchain includes feature extraction, training, and decoding. Additionally, Kaldi benefits from a robust community and extensive documentation, aiding users in troubleshooting and system improvement. Based on Kaldi, Vosk is designed to be lightweight and efficient. Therefore, it can be easily integrated into mobile and embedded applications, such as on devices with limited resources like the Raspberry Pi. Vosk stands out for its multilingual support, making it especially useful for applications targeting diverse user groups. It uses a pre-trained model and allows us to train the custom model. Its capability for real-time speech recognition with low-latency responses makes it ideal for interactive applications.

2.1 Dataset

The performance of ASR systems depend on high-quality, annotated speech datasets for effective training and testing. Datasets such as the Italian Spontaneous Dialogue Dataset [2] and the Common Voice project [3] provide a wide range of authentic speech samples, allowing ASR models to manage spontaneous speech, regional accents, and background noise. These resources are valuable for advancing voice assistants, automated transcription services, and accessibility tools tailored for Italian speakers.

Common Voice Mozilla’s Common Voice dataset is an open-source initiative [3]. It allows users to contribute by either recording texts or helping to verify if an audio recording matches its transcription. To date, the project has collected 18.6k hours of data across multiple languages, with 14.1k hours validated. The platform currently offers speech datasets in 112 languages and is continually updated. The information provided above is accurate as of May 2022.

Italian Spontaneous Dialogue Dataset The Italian (Italy) Spontaneous Dialogue Telephony speech dataset contains dialogues on over 20 topics. It includes transcriptions of 676 native speakers with text content, speaker ID, gender, age, and

other attributes. The dataset covers a wide range of geographic regions, improving model performance in real-world, complex tasks. The dataset ensures full compliance with data protection regulations and privacy standards, maintaining user privacy and legal rights throughout the collection, storage, and usage.

2.2 Evaluation criteria in ASR

Different metrics have been defined to evaluate the effectiveness and suitability of ASR techniques. In addition to classic metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, recall, precision, and specificity, specific metrics for ASR have also been established, including word error rate (WER), Word Recognition Rate (WRR), and Character error rate (CER) [20]. WER determines the ratio of incorrectly recognized words to the overall number of processed words, as follows

$$WER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (1)$$

Where I, D, S, H, and N denote the number of insertions, deletions, substitutions, hits, and input words, respectively. WRR, also known as the Word Accuracy Rate, is a variant of the WER used to measure the efficiency of an ASR. The metric is computed as follows

$$WRR = \frac{N - S - D - I}{N} = \frac{H - I}{N} \quad (2)$$

$H = N - (S + D)$ is the number of correctly predicted words. The CER follows the same evaluation principle, except that it measures errors in characters rather than words. The CER value can be determined using the equation below.

$$CER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (3)$$

Where S , D , and C denote the number of substitutions, insertions, deletions, and correct characters, respectively. N is the total number of characters in the source.

3 Experiments

We conducted experiments on the Common Voice dataset, focusing exclusively on the Italian language, to identify the optimal combination of ASR systems and spelling correction methods for real-time applications on devices with constrained computational resources. We selected Whisper and Vosk models and compared their performances before and after fine-tuning, which exploits the Italian part of the Common Voice dataset. The obtained results are reported in the Table 1. In particular, we fine-tuned the Whisper Base model with 74 million parameters, the Whisper Tiny model with 39 million parameters and Vosk. Whisper utilizes a Transformer architecture for its encoder and decoder, which

share an identical structural setup. In the Whisper Base and Tiny versions, the encoder and decoder consist of 16 and 6 Transformer blocks, respectively. Additionally, the convolutional layers at the encoder’s front end were initialized randomly, while the encoder’s CTC projection layer was initialized with weights from the word embeddings used in the decoder. During fine-tuning, all model parameters were updated using gradients. We set the batch size to 8 with a gradient accumulation of 4 to have an effective batch of 32 per step and the learning rate to $2.5e-05$, which is the one advised for fine-tuning this model with a warm-up linear learning rate scheduler that included 240 warm-up steps. The fine-tuning process consists of 5 epochs, and the final evaluation was based on the average of the model checkpoints from the epochs.

Vosk, suitable for working in devices with limited computational capacities, utilizes an architecture based on deep learning models. It combines deep neural networks, Deep Neural Network Hidden Markov Models (DNN-HMM) and RNN-LM, and Mel-frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) as an acoustic model based on Kaldi to extract features that are the input of DNN-HMM that associates MFCC to spoken language. After that, a n-gram language model combined with RNN-LM predicts the probability of a word based on the context. The fine-tuning process of a Vosk model is time-consuming. It requires updating the language model and using Kaldi scripts to recreate the acoustic model based on the dataset’s audio. For this reason, Vosk is only considered as a baseline for a small and fast model, suitable for devices with limited computational power, as the results obtained from the model were acceptable.

Model	WER	CER	Fine-Tune	WER(Fine-Tuned)	CER(Fine-Tuned)
Vosk-Small-It	40%		No	-	-
Whisper-Tiny	62%	24%	Yes	28.3%	10.08%
Whisper-Base	45%	16%	Yes	21.7%	7.28%

Table 1. Difference between the baseline and fine-tuned models

By observing the result reported in Table 1, we observe that the Whisper-Base outperforms the others. The Vosk-Small-It model, which serves as a baseline for low-resource devices, achieved a Word Error Rate (WER) of 40%. In contrast, the Whisper-Tiny model initially showed a higher WER of 62%, indicating a relatively poor performance for general ASR tasks. However, after finetuning, the Whisper-Tiny model significantly reduced WER, improving to 28.3%. Similarly, the Character Error Rate (CER) also improved to 10.08%. These results suggest that finetuning Whisper-Tiny on the Italian data substantially enhances its recognition capabilities, making it a viable option for tasks requiring higher accuracy. The Whisper-Base model demonstrated a WER of 45% in its baseline form, which was already an improvement compared to performance without the finetuning of Whisper-Tiny. After finetuning, Whisper-Base achieved a WER of 21.7%, the best performance among the models tested. The CER also showed a notable improvement, reaching 7.28%. The finetuning process signifi-

cantly improves the performance of Whisper models, especially Whisper-Base, which shows the most promising results for high-accuracy transcription tasks.

4 Conclusion and Future Works

In this paper, we conducted a comparative study to understand the best ASR systems for real-time applications on devices with constrained computational resources. We evaluated three widely used ASR systems: Whisher-tiny, Whisher-base, and Vosk API in Italian. Although significant progress has been made in recent years in ASR models, this progress has not been uniformly distributed across all languages, as the availability and quality of datasets heavily influence it. To understand such ASR systems for real-time applications, we fine-tuned the three pre-trained models using a public Italian dataset called the Common Voice dataset. The performances of the three models are comparable to those in the literature for English, the most commonly used language.

In future works, we consider other models, such as WavLM [13], SeamlessM4T [8] and DistilWhisper [16]. Moreover, we also intend to consider other datasets, such as the Italian Spontaneous Dialogue Dataset and Speech DatCar database [4], to study the robustness of such methods in noisy environments. To address the current limitations of spoken Italian datasets, we intend to develop a new dataset that expands demographic and linguistic diversity, including under-represented dialects, minority languages, and diverse speaker groups. Another challenge is to apply such systems to other scopes, like emotion recognition or stress detections from speech, to integrate different approaches based on analysis of wearable sensors data like proposed in [22, 26] Another challenging aspect is to extend the approach proposed in [10, 9] for programming Graph Neural Networks to transformers and DNN-HMMs in the ASR applicative scenarios.

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